

The Role of Legends in Teaching English for Foreigners “Munzur Legend”

ESMA UÇAR*

To cite this article: *Esma UÇAR, St. Clements University, Current Science, Volume 4, No. 6, 2022, p. 67-86. - 0099-0001-2206-0002*

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation and support processes to the international platform. (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Dr. Ugur Ugural

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Asst.Prof. Osman Doruk

"• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic journal with a multi-science peer-review." (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

• The magazine is published monthly.

"The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month." (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) process.

"• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days." (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.

ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE:

+49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

The Role of Legends in Teaching English for Foreigners “Munzur Legend”

ESMA UÇAR*

Abstract:

Turkish to foreigners along with the dissemination of education, researches are conducted to consider this education in the best way. With this product, the vaccination process, which can be measured as it belongs, as well as grammar, will not be completed to be used as the history of learning and facilitating the language used other than the native language. It is a region where language teaching is lacking in learning the vocabulary only by aiming at it. This will be one that will benefit from the use of that language when teaching a new language. In the teaching of Turkish to foreigners, the texts that will be made in the culture museum in the best way are folk products. In these texts, in which the Turkish peoples are reflected in the safest ways, in almost all cases, appropriate help is around the texts. This is important because of its position in the indicator for historical English in written and dictionary folk products. In this course, the example of the "Munzur legend", which is the legend of succeeding in attracting the young with the motifs in the language and the city it hosts, was examined in teaching Turkish to foreigners.

Keywords: Language, Culture, Teaching English for Foreigners , Legend

*Folk Literature Specialist, ucaresma2429@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0002-4799-1062

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, which is driven by technology, everything is changing and developing rapidly. Thanks to these developments, the interaction between countries in the political, economic, educational and cultural fields has increased. As such, learning a foreign language has become more compulsory. Today, learning a foreign language has become inevitable to be aware of the developments in the world, to follow science and technology, to provide trade between countries, and to establish many necessary political and social relations. So much so that this situation has become a language trade all over the world and people have started to allocate serious budgets for language learning. Turkey has now taken its place on this language trade page, taking important steps to teach its language to the entire world, with Turkish language trainings held within the framework of TÖMER coordinators affiliated with universities and foundations or education institutes abroad. With these steps taken, the demands of foreigners to learn Turkish continue to increase day by day.

Teaching Turkish to foreigners has reached a prominent position in recent years for new research and investigations. Various academic studies are conducted on teaching Turkish to foreigners by introducing different techniques and methods. There are four different language skills in teaching Turkish to foreigners. These are reading comprehension, listening, writing and speaking. All foreign students, who maximize these four skills, can express themselves in the most accurate way both in their education life and in their daily life. Reading texts are important for foreign students to develop their vocabulary and to think in Turkish. For this reason, in teaching Turkish to foreigners, reading texts should be selected by considering the students' levels. While choosing these texts, the aim should not be just to teach Turkish. In addition to teaching the Turkish language, it should be aimed to transfer Turkish culture as well. A language should not be taught independently of the culture of that nation. Because this situation can lead to the lack of richness of the language. For this reason, it would be a good decision to benefit from Turkish folk culture texts in teaching Turkish to foreigners. Tales, anecdotes, legends and epics are important writing types in which each nation reflects its own culture. *“ This world includes Folk Literature or Folklore products, and these products constitute the most important building materials of Turkish culture. From proverbs, idioms,*

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.

**ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE
TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE:
+49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

tales, epics, legends, anecdotes, folk tales and even folk poetry, many folkloric products that have been the property of the people of a nation, preserved in the memory of the people for centuries and transferred from generation to generation, are among the elements that best reflect the simple style of Turkish, hence its essence . , 2014: 1483). The texts selected from these genres will attract the attention of foreign students and will facilitate their language learning.

1. WHAT IS LANGUAGE?

Language is the basic constituent element that provides understanding between people. Man is born into his own language and thus creates his own field of existence. Language is a person's area of existence transformed into voice, writing and body language. Each nation and the individuals that compose it gain an identity in their own language universe. In this respect, language is an expression of values from the past, mentality and psychology, individual and society. (Sahin, 2014: 828). Language is the science in which feelings and thoughts are expressed with sounds or signs. The ancient language is especially important for people to communicate. Language is a means of self-expression and expresses the important concept that we can call the key to life that conveys the dose of emotions and the essence of thought. Every nation, every state, even every community has diversified by contributing to the development of language. Expressing the language with symbols other than its discourse also led to the formation of different alphabets. Language is a crucial step from primitiveness to civilization, language is wealth, language is freedom. Language is the healthiest form of communication. In other words, language is *the science that makes people come together as a society, a nation and finally a civilization* (Şimşek, 2021: 4).

2. WHAT IS CULTURE?

Culture is the legacy of ornate and artistic actions and situations that stand out from the ordinary life of a nation. Culture is a system of common values that creates a society by gathering independent communities on the same denominator and establishes an invisible bond between people. Culture has been used as the universal name of the efforts of societies to reach a useful purpose for themselves and all the products they produce because of these efforts. With this

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE
TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE:
+49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

use of culture, besides being historical, it brings people to the forefront as an element that changes and shapes nature for its own purposes (Özlem, 2000: 146). The people of the same society build their lives on the life of that geography. For this reason, the culture has persisted for centuries. Sulhi Dönmezer considered the concept of culture as “a complex whole consisting of knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs and traditions and all abilities acquired as a member of human society” (Dönmezer, 1982:116). As it can be understood from here, the common denominator of societies, states and even nations have always been their culture. For this reason, culture; A nation's religion, belief system, clothing, holidays, habits, attitudes, customs and traditions that affect and sometimes even form the whole set of values.

3. RELATIONSHIP OF LANGUAGE AND CULTURE

Making one's life easier by adapting to society is related to recognizing the culture of that society. Culture is not just about actions or traditional rituals that are repeated at regular intervals. One of the most important sources of culture is language. While language is especially important for the transmission of culture, culture also serves the richness of the language. In this regard, Yazoğlu said, “ *Man is only human thanks to his language. In that case, language unites the social entity called nation and creates a flow of emotion and thought among its members* ” and emphasized the relationship between culture and language (Yazoğlu, 2005:122). Every individual born learns the language that is kneaded with his own culture from the very first moment. Language, which has its own characteristics, did not develop in a separate place from culture. Each language formed is fed from its own geography. For this reason, the voice of each geography is the source of the language of the people of that geography. However, it cannot be expected that different societies will show the same language development. If nature sings different songs in every geography. In some geographies, the only sound that drowns out the sound of the dry breeze is the sound of buzzing insects, while in some geographies the song of lightning strikes or yours. " A nation 's *history, geography, religious values, folklore, music, art, literature, science, world view and all kinds of common values that make it a nation are symbolized in words filtered through the filter of centuries. Thus, language becomes the mirror of social structure and culture.* " (Barın, 2004: 19). Every geography has formed its own language within the framework of certain rules. No language that develops in its own geography is independent of culture. Culture is the whole of unwritten

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE
TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE:
+49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

rules that that society has made a habit throughout its life. Everything that interferes with the life of society is the subject of language.

4. THE PLACE OF CULTURE IN TEACHING TURKISH TO FOREIGNERS

Pursuing the aim of teaching only language in foreign language teaching will be a deficient attitude to teach a foreign language. Being familiar with the culture of the language learned in foreign language learning is a factor that will facilitate language learning. “ A foreign language always brings with it a foreign culture. For individuals to understand the language better, it is especially important to learn the cultural characteristics of the country in which they learned the language. It is an undeniable fact that language and culture are inseparable parts, and that culture should also be learned in language learning” (İşcan and Yassıtaş, 2018: 47). While teaching Turkish to foreigners , it is necessary to talk about the development process of the language and to use teaching materials that reflect the culture of that language. Teaching languages to foreigners by using the right materials and helpful resources will be both more fun and more instructive. Today, many foreigners from abroad come to our country for educational purposes. This number is increasing every year.

Today, "Teaching Turkish to Foreigners", which is open to developments and changes, has been the subject of many researches and will continue to be. Language development of people begins in the womb and learning a native language is different from learning a foreign language because it is learned with experience. The most important reason students have learning difficulties while teaching Turkish to foreigners is that their own culture does not have the same characteristics as Turkish culture. Barın said, “*Teaching Turkish to foreigners aims to teach Turkish culture. Because language is the transmitter of culture. The different and difficult aspect of teaching Turkish as a foreign language from teaching it as a native language; He emphasized that foreign language teaching is different from learning a native language and culture is important for the realization of this learning* (Barn, 2008: 61). A student from Kazakhstan who is studying to learn Turkish in Turkey and a student from Somalia will have different learning difficulties. Kazakh language and culture are close to Turkish language and culture, so a Kazakh student will learn more quickly. However, Somalia is quite different from Turkey both in terms of language and culture. For this reason, these students will learn more difficult than Kazakh students while learning Turkish.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

The student who learns Turkish together with Turkish culture will be able to put the language on a more solid ground. Because no matter how much the student develops his/her vocabulary, he/she will still need a cultural background to understand stereotypes such as idioms and proverbs in our language. For this reason, Turkish should be taught by blending it with Turkish culture. Turkish culture has rich content in this sense. Folk literature texts have a structure to reflect Turkish culture within the scope of teaching Turkish to foreigners. Among these, tales, anecdotes, epics and legends can be considered as auxiliary texts in teaching Turkish to foreigners. Akyaka, who makes research on the type of anecdote, which is one of the anonymous folk literature products in teaching Turkish to foreigners, said, “ *The products that best reflect the culture are the types such as fairy tales, legends and anecdotes produced by the people who create and keep the culture alive.*” In his words, he emphasized the importance of folk literature products in teaching Turkish to foreigners. (Akkaya, 2013: 176). In other words, “ *The use of both written and oral/anonymous texts, including Turkish culture, as course materials, and in this context, the transfer of culture along with language is important in teaching Turkish to foreigners*” (Turhan Tuna, 2014: 1487).

Folk literature texts have managed to spread many grammar topics into the content of the text with the stereotyped expressions, idioms, proverbs and rhymes they contain. It is possible to find folk literature prose types suitable for all levels in teaching Turkish to foreigners. Among these prose types, legends are among the appropriate genres for cultural transfer in teaching Turkish to foreigners. The fact that it provides information about the cultural elements, motifs and the history of the geography that is narrated distinguishes it from other narrative types. “ *Legends; They are important cultural values that are shaped according to the experiences of societies, become evident as a product of the common cultural heritage, and shed light on social beliefs and values.* (Dağdeviren, 2009: 48).

5. A LEGEND IN TEACHING TURKISH TO FOREIGNERS

Legends are products of oral folk culture that will attract the attention of people of almost all ages, created by each nation with a little history, a little geography, and a little imagination. Legend is a concept used for short and oral folk culture products that describe historical and religious events with extraordinary qualities and miracles (Aslan, 2017: 362). *Legends are an oral folk product, which we can call the most beautiful expression of culture, which mirrors*

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE
TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE:
+49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

the social life of the society they belong to from the past to the present, enables many experiences that have left their mark on the life stage to find expression, and which corresponds to the fantastic world that human beings have in their minds despite the modern physical laws (Dağdeviren, 2009). : 41). Legends are not purely fictional texts. The village and town mentioned in many legends also exist. There are no completely fictional places like in fairy tales. Although the legends are among the fantastic literary products, they have managed to be more convincing and more remarkable with the traces they carry from history. Every beautiful place seen, or strangely conspicuous place has a story. These stories are told enrichingly from language to language, and over time they become the legend of that region. Although the motifs in the legends are remarkably like each other, each legend leaves its own flavor to the languages.

The use of legends in teaching Turkish to foreigners is an important source for the transfer of culture as well as language teaching. What should be considered here is whether the chosen legend is suitable for which level. It is necessary to transfer both the linguistic knowledge and the cultural treasure it contains to the student in the most accurate way. As an example, "The Legend of Munzur" has been examined in this article. It was stated that it would be appropriate to use this legend text as a supplementary text for students at A2 level.

5.1. Munzur Legend

"There was an honest and pure shepherd named Munzur who was herding the sheep of an agha who lived in the village of Ziyaret in the Ovacık district of Tunceli province. The agha, who had no children, loved Munzur as his own child.

Aga went on a pilgrimage one day. While his proprietor was on pilgrimage, Munzur went to his landlord's wife and said:

"Girl; My brother wants hot halvah, if you make it, I'll take it to him." said.

The lady was first surprised by what the shepherd Munzur said, and then:

"I guess the poor shepherd wants to eat halvah, he is ashamed to say it directly, he uses his landlord as an excuse, so let me make him a halva so he can eat it." he cooks the halvah. He ties it into a bundle and says to Munzur:

"Here, my son, take it to your master." says.

At that time, the agha is praying on the pilgrimage. While saluting left and right during the prayer, he also looks at Munzur standing next to him with a bundle in his hand. After finishing his prayer, he said to Munzur:

"Welcome son, what are you doing here, what is that in your hand?" says.

Munzur:

"My brother, you wanted hot halvah, I brought it." he says and hands the bundle to his proprietor.

Its agha opens the package and sees that there is a warm halva in it. He remains in awe . When he turns his head, he sees that Munzur has disappeared.

When the agha fulfills his pilgrimage and returns to his village, his neighbors go to meet the pilgrim with gifts. Munzur, on the other hand, goes to meet his proprietor with some milk milked from the sheep into his bowl because he has no gift to take.

When he saw Agha Munzur, he said to his companions:

"The real pilgrim is Munzur. The hand to be kissed is Munzur's hand. I will kiss his hand first." he says and runs towards Munzur.

When Munzur heard the speeches:

"Oh, my brother, for God's sake, nothing like that will happen. I grew up on your bread for years. How dare you kiss my hand! I won't let you kiss my hand." he starts to run away. Munzur is in the front, the agha and his followers are behind, a chase begins. When they came to the place where the current Munzur river comes out, Munzur's foot tripped on a stone and the bowl full of milk in his hand was poured out. From the place where the milk is poured, a white-water gushes like milk. Then Munzur starts running again and takes another forty steps. Every step he takes, a stream of water gushes. A river emerges from these gushing waters.

Those who run after Munzur cannot go beyond this river, Munzur is lost in these mountains" (Aslan, 2017: 367-368).

5.1.1. Evaluation of Munzur Legend in Terms of Time-Space and Motifs

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

When we look at the plot, everything that was told at the beginning was in accordance with the normal flow of life, but extraordinary events started to happen when the agha went to pilgrimage. The religious motifs seen in the legends caused a radical change in the content of almost all types of oral literature in Turkish society, especially after the adoption of Islam. These oral narratives, in which religious reflections are intensely seen, are the barest form of folk culture.

Time: The Munzur legend is an example of a legend that tells how the Munzur river was formed, with extraordinary events. When examined historically, there is no definite information about when the Munzur river was formed. For this reason, the time is uncertain in the Munzur legend. Foreign students are asked about the concept of time in the legends in their own society and their thoughts about the reality of time are taken. From this point of view, it is stated that the concept of time in legends is also uncertain in different societies . Thus, it is ensured that the legend-time relationship is formed in the minds of the students.

Place: In the Munzur legend, the place is expressed very clearly by writing as the Visit village of Ovacık district of Tunceli province, relative to the time. The place where the event takes place is a real place that is concrete in the real world. The fact that the place is real is the key to escape from the fantasy world where the student is trapped in fairy tales. This distinguishes myth from fairy tales. Because the places in fairy tales are fictional and fantastic. In fairy tales, the heroes go on a difficult journey and this journey is usually to Kafdagi. The clear and true expressions in the legend separate the legends from the fairy tales and allow us to look at the legend more realistically. In fact, Munzur river takes its source from the visiting hill in Ovacık district of Tunceli province. Based on this information, it is stated that a narrative about the river located in the borders of Turkey is exhibited, enabling students to think about the realism of the legend-space relationship.

Shepherd: There is an honest and pure shepherd named Munzur. The inside of the legend, which is processed over a real place , is decorated with a fairy-tale hero. Legends that speak of both history, geography and literature are quite remarkable texts in this respect. It is a customary situation in many oral literature products that the hero appears as a shepherd. In many fictional texts, the hero is a poor shepherd, and it is told that the shepherd had a miracle or how his fortunes turned. In this text, the protagonist is the shepherd and has a miracle. When this secret is revealed, he disappears, leaving the Munzur river behind. The shepherd motif

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE
TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE:
+49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

plays the role of protagonist or assistant hero in legends and epics, especially in fairy tales. In Dede Korkut Book, the shepherd is both immensely powerful and possessed of miracles in the story "The Boy where Salur Kazan's House was Plundered". Karaçuk, who dreams that Şökli Melik will attack, takes his shepherd brothers with him and fights against the enemy. While he fought fearlessly, showing his courage and strength, seeing this in his dream before the enemy attacked was an indication of his miraculousness. Köksel said, “ *Karaçuk Shepherd, who is seen as extraordinary, only has a slingshot and is fighting against three hundred people. In Dede Korkut, the shepherd has the strength that we often do not see even in the protagonist in the stories. In the story, Salur, who represents the alpine type with his strength and courage, is ahead of Kazan. Karaçuk Shepherd exhibits a mythological hero model with his invincibility. Like mythological heroes, he has superior strength and courage. The dream of Karaçuk Shepherd before the infidel raid shows that he is not an ordinary hero.* ” (Köksel, 2012: 80).

Emphasizing that the shepherd is a person who acts in accordance with the customs and traditions in the legend is important for foreign students to learn what customs, traditions and customs are in a different society. It is aimed to create these feelings in students by emphasizing the importance of many social notions such as respecting the elder, being loyal to the door where he eats bread, and having a sense of responsibility towards the place where he works.

Childlessness Motif: Childlessness motif has an especially prominent place in Turkish folk literature. Events often develop around the motif of childlessness. A childless person either embarks on a magical journey or has a child if he fulfills certain conditions. In Dede Korkut stories, gentlemen who do not have children are hosted in the black tent and punished in a way. In the Munzur legend, the property owner of the village does not have a child. That's why the agha loves Munzur as his own child. Munzur is a shepherd, but he is a shepherd whom the village lord, who has no children, loves like his son. Although this may seem like a small detail, it is the first quality that meets Munzur's condition of being the protagonist. For this reason, it is necessary to understand the cause-and-effect relationship between the events well and to transfer them to the student in its simplest form. By expressing the importance of the concept of child and family in Turkish society around this motif, foreign students are informed about the Turkish family structure. It is expressed that families who do not have children love them like their own children by adopting them, and that the child adopts that family in the same way, emphasizing that in addition to blood ties, the feeling of fidelity has a unifying structure for people.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.

**ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE
TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE:
+49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

Religious Motifs: With the adoption of Islam, religious motifs began to appear in many oral products. For example, in the Dede Korkut stories, all the gentlemen would come together and pray, and their prayers would be accepted. In this text, religious motifs are mentioned about going to pilgrimage and praying. Going on pilgrimage is a requirement of Islam and is a sacred duty for every Muslim. After the legend is taught in the classroom, it should be processed in detail, emphasizing all the motifs. With this legend, foreign students will both expand their vocabulary and learn about the Islamic belief system. In addition, the religious rituals of students belonging to different religions are discussed and the relationship between religion and culture is revealed.

Number Forty : "Munzur takes forty steps, and the river is formed."

The number forty is among the formulaic numbers considered sacred in Turkish folk culture. *The number forty, which is used in many fields from folk literature to mysticism, from idioms and proverbs to folk beliefs, has attracted the attention of researchers with this aspect. The first thought that comes to mind as an answer to the question of why the number is widely used is the reflection of numbers and symbols, which are connected to religious beliefs or in other words, religious values are ascribed to life. These beliefs come to life with many practices that people do in daily life* (Guvenc, 2009: 86). There are various idioms and stereotyped expressions on the number forty in Turkish folk culture.

The number forty, which is used in many fields from folk literature to mysticism, from idioms and proverbs to folk beliefs, has attracted the attention of researchers with this aspect. The first thought that comes to mind as an answer to the question of why the number is widely used is the reflection of numbers and symbols, which are connected to religious beliefs or in other words, religious values are ascribed to life. These beliefs come to life with many practices that people do in daily life.

Mixing with the Forties: Forty people, who come across as dervish type, are saints and have extraordinary characteristics. When the secret of these people is revealed, they disappear immediately, and they are never heard from again.

Forty days and forty nights wedding: Two young people who love each other in fairy tales, overcoming many difficulties, finally get together and get married in a wedding that will last for forty days and forty nights.

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE
TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE:
+49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

The emergence of forty: In Turkish culture, when someone dies, a mawlid is read on the third, seventh and fortieth days and a charity meal is distributed. In addition, it is believed that the mother giving birth and the newly born baby are in danger for forty days and are kept under protection. Many religious rituals are performed for forty days, and at the end of forty days, the forty of the mothers and her baby are flown in the ceremony. (Karakas, 2013: 62-63).

When we look at the products of Turkish folk literature, we see that the number forty is frequently used. In the stories of Dede Korkut, there are forty valiant and forty thin-waisted girls. Hz. The prophet is given prophecy at the age of 40. A person must give zakat one-fourth of his property. It is mentioned about forty thieves who covet people's property. (Guvenc, 2009: 90-92).

To put it briefly, the number forty is frequently encountered in fairy tales, legends, epics, religious beliefs and in our daily lives.

Motif of Extracting Water from the Ground: The agha, who told the villager that Munzur showed miracles, wanted to kiss Munzur's hand. Munzur does not want to have his hand kissed because he grew up with his bread and vaccine and runs away. As he runs away, the milk in his hand spills out and water gushes out from there. Then he takes forty steps, and a river is formed as wide as this step. Especially in the legends, the motif of removing water from the ground is frequently encountered. Many legends are about how a mountain, a river, a rock came into being. Kumartaşlıoğlu said the following about the motif of removing water from the ground. “ *The people who extract the water in these legends are either great personalities of the Islamic world such as Hazrat Ali or local personalities who lived in the area where the water is located and are known by the people of that region.* ” (Kumartaşlıoğlu, 2016: 120). Munzur also lived in that region for years and has now become one of the local people. However, when his miracle was revealed, he disappeared, leaving a river behind.

The Motif of Going Far Away at a Time: The fact that Munzur Agha knew that he was craving hot halvah while on pilgrimage and that he disappeared by taking this halvah to him before it got cold is a sign of miracle. It is an extraordinary situation that is not possible under normal conditions for Munzur to go to a different place, independent of where he is. The motif of being able to go long distances at once, also called Tayyi space, is frequently encountered in Turkish folk literature products. If we give an example of the motif of being able to go far away at once, there is a person named Aziz Baba, who is believed to have a miracle, living in

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.

**ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE
TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE:
+49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

the town of Ulalar in Erzincan. It is believed that Aziz Baba helped Turkish soldiers by participating in the Korean War. Aziz Baba, who helped the army by participating in the Korean War, is also in Erzincan. (Bezgin, 2019: 125). It is stated that some extraordinary events are placed in the legends by explaining the motives of removing water from the ground and going far away to the students.

Cultural Elements: Respect for elders: It is especially important to show respect to elders in Turkish folk culture. People avoid making the slightest disrespect to their elders and they do not fail to show respect. Munzur also pays homage to his property owner, whom he grew up with and whose bread he ate. After the aghas returned from the pilgrimage, he wanted to kiss Munzur's hand because of the miracle he showed, but Munzur refused to accept this because of the respect he felt for the aghas and fled. Respecting and respecting elders has always been important in Turkish culture. There are many examples that are reflected in our daily life.

Not to go to see someone coming from afar empty-handed: Villagers who go to see the agha coming from the pilgrimage do not go empty-handed. Everyone brings their own gift. Since Munzur has no presents to take, he takes the milk he milked from the sheep. In Turkish folk culture, when he goes to see someone from afar, there is a tradition to bring anything he or she may need to that person's home. These can be fruits, vegetables, drinks or any souvenirs. In Turkish culture, not only when visiting someone from afar, but also when visiting someone's house or going to a funeral home, anything they may need is brought to their home.

CONCLUSION

Cultural transfer in teaching Turkish to foreigners provides an accurate and holistic education by expanding the semantic field of the language. While teaching Turkish to foreigners, it is especially important to choose the texts that take place in the folk culture and touch on the customs and traditions of that culture. To be able to transfer culture as well as language in teaching Turkish to foreigners, the selected texts should reflect the Turkish culture. For this reason, it would be the right choice to make use of tales, legends and epics, which are Turkish folk literature products, as auxiliary texts. Among these genres, it is the type of legend that will appeal to all ages and arouse the curiosity of people. Although legends are among the fantastic text types, the real elements they contain make us believe in them. The use of such texts, which make people think, in language teaching helps to convey the culture of that language along

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.

**ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE
TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE:
+49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

with the language to the student. For this reason, it would be an excellent choice to make use of legends in teaching Turkish to foreigners. The point to be considered here is which level of students these legends are suitable for. As a result of this study, it is understood that Munzur Legend, whose plot and motifs are examined, has a rich content that will reflect Turkish culture in many ways. It can be concluded that Munzur Legend is appropriate to be read as a supplementary text to A2-level students when both its subject, the simplicity of its language, and the rich Turkish culture motifs it contains are examined. The text should be read first and then culture transfer should be conducted by giving examples from Turkish culture through its motifs. The text is written in a simple and understandable language.

It is important in terms of cultural transfer to make use of Turkish folk literature products as auxiliary texts in teaching Turkish to foreigners. Language is not independent of culture and the two complement each other like a puzzle. Language, which is independent of culture, loses its sense and means nothing but stereotypes. However, culture is wealth, and it is possible to convey this wealth only by using language.

REFERENCES

- ASLAN, E. (2007). Turkish Folk Literature, Pegem Academy. Anadolu Academy Journal of Social Sciences, 1(2): 123-138
- BARIN, E. (2004). "Principles in Teaching Turkish to Foreigners", Hacettepe University Turkic Studies Studies (HUTAD), 1(19): 19-30.
- BARIN, E. (2008). "The Role of Nasreddin Hodja Jokes in Teaching Turkish to Foreigners", Türk Yurdu Dergisi, 255: 61-63.
- BEZGIN, YK (2019). Miraculous Motifs in the Legends of Erzincan Parents",
- DAGDEVIREN, I. (2009). Evaluation of Cultural Transfer Based on Legendary Texts in Teaching Turkish to Foreigners, Unpublished Master's Thesis, Bursa Uludağ University Institute of Educational Sciences, Bursa.
- DÖNMEZLER, S. (1982) Sociology, Savaş Publications, Ankara.
- SAFE. A. O. (2009). "An Investigation on the Use of the Number Forty in Folk

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

- Literature”, A.Ü. Journal of Turkic Studies Institute, 16(41): 59-75.
- İŞCAN, A., YASSITAS, T. (2018). “Cultural Transfer in Textbooks for Teaching Turkish as a Foreign Language: Example of Seven Climate Turkish Teaching Sets (B1-B2 Level)”, Aydın TÖMER Language Journal, 3(1): 47-66.
- KAPLAN, M. (2007). Culture and Language, Dergah Publications, Istanbul.
- KARAKAS, R. (2013). “The Concept of 'Forty' and 'Beliefs and Practices Around the Subtraction of Forty' in Diyarbakir”, Journal of Turkic Studies, 33: 59-75.
- KÖKSEL, B. (2012). “Religious-Mythological Supporting Hero Motif in the Book of Dede Korkut”, Turkish Journal of Social Research, 16(1): 73-88.
- KUMATAŞLIOĞLU, S. (2016). From Miracle to Miracle: "Getting Water from the Ground" Motif Legends, Hacettepe University Journal of Turkic Studies, 25: 119-140.
- OGUZ, ES (2011). “The Concept of Culture in Social Sciences”, Journal of the Faculty of Letters, 28(2): 123-139.
- ORUC, S. (2016). Mother Tongue and Mother Tongue in Turkish, Journal of Turkish Language and Literature, 2(5): 311-322.
- ŞİMŞEK, P. (2021). Reading Texts and Supplementary Books in Teaching Turkish to Foreigners, Unpublished Master's Thesis, Afyon Kocatepe University Institute of Social Sciences, Afyon.
- TURHAN TUNA, S. (2014). “The Use of Folk Literature Texts in Teaching Turkish to Foreigners: The Example of Oğuz Kağan Epic”, Turkish Studies, 9(3): 1481-1497.
- YAZOGLU, R. (2005). “Language-Culture Relationship”, Conservative Thought, 2(5): 223-143.

EXTENDED SUMMARY

Language is the basic constituent element that provides understanding between people. Human is born into his own language and thus creates his own field of existence. Language is a person's area of existence transformed into voice, writing and body language. Each nation and the individuals that compose it gain an identity in their own language universe. In this respect, language is an expression of values from the past, mentality and psychology, individual and society. Culture is the legacy of ornate and artistic actions and situations that stand out from the ordinary life of a nation. Culture is a system of common values that creates an invisible bond between people by gathering independent communities on the same denominator. The people of the same society build their lives on the life of that geography. Making one's life easier by adapting to society is related to recognizing the culture of that society. Culture is not just about actions or traditional rituals that are repeated at regular intervals. One of the most important sources of culture is language. While language is especially important for the transmission of culture, culture also serves the richness of the language. Language is not independent of culture and the two complement each other like a puzzle. Language, which is independent of culture, loses its sense and means nothing but stereotypes. However, culture is wealth, and it is possible to convey this wealth only by using language. For this reason, aiming to teach only language in foreign language teaching will be an incomplete attitude to teach a foreign language. A foreign language always brings with it a foreign culture. It is especially important for individuals to know the cultural characteristics of the country where they learned the language so that they can better understand that language while learning a new language. While teaching Turkish to foreigners, it is necessary to talk about the development process of the language and to use teaching materials that reflect the culture of that language. By using the right materials and helpful resources, teaching foreign languages will be both more fun and more informative. The student who learns Turkish together with Turkish culture will be able to put the language on a more solid ground. No matter how much the student develops his/her vocabulary, he/she will

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.

**ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE
TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE:
+49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

still need a cultural background to understand stereotypes such as idioms and proverbs in our language. For this reason, Turkish should be taught by blending it with Turkish culture. Turkish culture contains rich contents in this sense. Folk literature texts have also a structure to reflect Turkish culture within the scope of teaching Turkish to foreigners. Tales, anecdotes, epics and legends can be considered as auxiliary texts in teaching Turkish to foreigners. Among these, legends are important sources for the transfer of Turkish culture as well as being used in teaching Turkish language to foreigners. The discussed "Legend of Munzur" will be discussed in terms of time, place, hero and motifs, and information will be given to foreign students about Turkish culture and traditions included in the legend. Students from diverse cultures will have the opportunity to compare this legend, which contains many features of Turkish culture and life, with an event or legend in their own society. As a result of this study, it is understood that Munzur Legend, whose plot and motifs are examined, has a rich content that will reflect Turkish culture in many ways. It can be concluded that Munzur Legend should be read as a supplementary text to A2-level students when both its subject, the simplicity of its language, and the rich Turkish culture motifs it contains are examined. The text should be read first and then culture transfer should be conducted by giving examples from Turkish culture through its motifs. In this way, foreign students will both increase their Turkish vocabulary and enable them to get to know Turkish culture more closely. Because the transfer of culture in teaching Turkish to foreigners provides an accurate and holistic education by expanding the semantic field of the language.